

A Study of Relationship Between Spiritual Intelligence and Emotional Intelligence of the Students Studying at Secondary Level

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Abstract

The purpose of the present study is to measure the relationship between Spiritual Intelligence & Emotional Intelligence of secondary level students of Shamli. This is a survey study under descriptive research. The present study students at secondary level have been considered as the Population regardless of their gender. Thus the result of the Present study will only be applicable to this population of secondary level students. In order to draw representative sample 100 students studying at secondary level and professional streams in Shamli District U.P. have been chosen through randomization. For the collection of data the researcher administered the Spiritual Intelligence constructed by Prof. Roquiya Zainuddin & Ms. Anjum Ahmed and Emotional Intelligence constructed by S. K. Mangal & Shubhra Mangal. After collection of data relationship between variables has been sought with the help of product moment coefficient of correlation and the results were analyzed and interpretations were drawn. The results obtained were checked at both the level of significance i.e. at 0.01 and 0.05. It was observed from the findings that no significant relationship exist between Spiritual Intelligence and its components and Emotional Intelligence of the students studying at secondary level.

Keyword: Spiritual Intelligence, Emotional intelligence, Secondary level students.

Introduction

Today the field of psychology has shown the tendency towards the spiritual dimensions and wide horizons for extended research has spread that can reflect the profound influence of spiritual forces on the human body and mind and makes clear the importance of spiritual intelligence. Spiritual approaches to health and sciences, for researchers and mental health professionals have recently been emphasized. Some research studies have paid to the effect of spirituality on the overall health of the individuals. Mental health professionals have recognized the power of spiritual intelligence, some of which are defined as capacity to feel, understand and present the highest part of themselves, others and the world around.

Spirituality is derived from the Latin word "Spirare" meaning to breathe. Spirituality is inherent aspect of human nature and essence of our existence so it draws attention of many theorists as the source of all thoughts, feelings, values and behavior.

Emotional Intelligence the most popular, researched, dynamic construct of 21st century has drawn the attention of academicians and researchers. EI emphasize the role of emotion in a emotions in a individual success or failure in work place and in life.

John D. Mayer and Peter Salovey (1990) has defined Emotional Intelligence (EI) is "the ability to monitor one's own and other's feeling and emotions, to discriminate among them and to use this information to guide one's thinking and actions." Interest in emotional intelligence has grown significantly since the 1990s, with research suggesting that good emotional understanding can lead to increased social effectiveness.

An analysis of emotional intelligence was found in thousands of men and women which showed that women, on average, are more aware of their emotions, show more empathy and are more self-confident, optimistic and adaptable. It was found that men are also able to handle stress better than women. In general however, far more similarities exist than difference. Some men are empathetic as the most interpersonally sensible women are while some women are just as able to withstand stress as the most emotionally resilient men.

Need and Significance of the Study

The study is needed and significant from several points of view not only in bringing excellence among individuals but also in revealing the probable interplay between cognitive and non-cognitive aspects of education. Besides cognitive competence and skills, there is a need of skills which will build up spiritual development.

Emotional intelligence is an attempt to extend one's understanding of intelligence. For solving the problems or taking decision EQ works with IQ. Spiritual intelligence and emotional intelligence are dependent on the environment. There is ample scope for its development at any stage.

Statement of the Problem

"A Study of Relationship Between Spiritual Intelligence and Emotional Intelligence of the students studying at secondary level."

Objectives

1. To study the relationship between Spiritual Intelligence and Emotional Intelligence of the students studying at secondary level.
2. To study the relationship between The Inner Self, component of Spiritual Intelligence and Emotional Intelligence of the students studying at secondary level.
3. To study the relationship between The Interself, component of Spiritual Intelligence and Emotional Intelligence of the students studying at
4. To study the relationship between Biostoria, component of Spiritual Intelligence and Emotional Intelligence of the students studying at secondary level.
5. To study the relationship between Life Perspectives, component of Spiritual Intelligence and Emotional Intelligence of the students studying at secondary level.
6. To study the relationship between Spiritual Actualization, component of Spiritual Intelligence and Emotional Intelligence of the students studying at secondary level.
7. To study the relationship between Value Orientation, component of Spiritual Intelligence and Emotional Intelligence of the students studying at secondary level.

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant relationship between Spiritual Intelligence and Emotional Intelligence of the students studying at secondary level.
2. There is no significant relationship between The Inner Self, component of Spiritual Intelligence and Emotional Intelligence of the students studying at secondary level.
3. There is no significant relationship between The Interself, component of Spiritual Intelligence and Emotional Intelligence of the students studying at secondary level.
4. There is no significant relationship between Biostoria, component of Spiritual Intelligence and Emotional Intelligence of the students studying at secondary level.
5. There is no significant relationship between Life Perspectives, component of Spiritual Intelligence and Emotional Intelligence of the students studying at secondary level.
6. There is no significant relationship between Spiritual Actualization, component of Spiritual Intelligence and Emotional Intelligence of the students studying at secondary level.
7. There is no significant relationship between Value Orientation, component of Spiritual Intelligence and Emotional Intelligence of the students studying at secondary level.

Delimitation of the Study

1. The present study has been confined to students studying at Secondary Level.
2. The present study has been confined to students U.P. Board.

3. The present study has been confined to students at studying Shamli District U.P.

Methodology

The descriptive survey research method has been applied in the study.

Population of the Sample

The present study students at secondary level have been considered as the Population regardless of their gender. Thus the result of the Present study will only be applicable to this population of secondary level students.

In order to draw representative sample 100 students studying at secondary level and professional streams in Shamli District U.P. have been chosen through randomization.

Variables

Independent Variables : Spiritual Intelligence

Dependent Variables : Emotional Intelligence

Tools

"Roqan Spiritual Intelligence constructed by 'Prof. Roquiya Zainuddin' & Ms. Anjum Ahmed."

"Emotional Intelligence Inventory constructed by Dr. S. K. Mangal & Mrs. Shubhra Mangal "

Statistical Techniques

Product moment co-efficient of correlation 'r' has been used to measure the relationship between Spiritual Intelligence and Emotional Intelligence

Data Analysis and Interpretation

To test the relationship between the two variables of the study Pearson's Product Moment correlation technique was applied. Significance of correlation coefficient was checked afterwards to test the significance of the hypothesis.

The results obtained are mentioned in the table given below.

TABLE

Sr.No	Relationship between Variables	r - value	Level of Sig.
1.	Spiritual Intelligence and Emotional Intelligence	0.2223	Sig. at 0.05 level
2.	The Inner Self, component of Spiritual Intelligence and Emotional Intelligence	-0.0592	NS
3.	The Interself, component of Spiritual Intelligence and Emotional Intelligence	0.0797	NS
4.	Biostoria, component of Spiritual Intelligence and Emotional Intelligence	0.1611	NS
5.	Life Perspectives, component of Spiritual Intelligence and Emotional Intelligence	0.1226	NS
6.	Spiritual Actualization, component of Spiritual Intelligence and Emotional Intelligence	0.1240	NS
7.	Value Orientation, component of Spiritual Intelligence and Emotional Intelligence	0.2633	Significant at 0.01 and 0.05 level

Findings of the study

The first hypothesis of the study was there is no significant relationship between Spiritual Intelligence and Emotional Intelligence of the students studying at secondary level. Obtained 'r' value is zero point +0.2223. Thus there is positive but negligible relationship between both the variables. While considering the critical value of 'r' it was found that obtained 'r' value is significant at 0.05 level of confidence hence it may be interpreted that significant relationship exist between Spiritual Intelligence and Emotional Intelligence of the students studying at secondary level. Thus null hypothesis that there is significant relationship between Spiritual Intelligence and Emotional Intelligence of the students studying at secondary level is rejected. Sign shows that Spiritual

Intelligence and Emotional Intelligence of the students studying at secondary level have positive correlation.

The second hypothesis of the study was there is no significant between The Inner Self, component of Spiritual Intelligence and Emotional Intelligence of the students studying at secondary level. Obtained 'r' value is zero point -0.0592. Thus there is negative but negligible relationship between both the variables. While considering the critical value of 'r' it was found that obtained 'r' value is not significant at both the levels of confidence hence it may be interpreted that no significant relationship exist between The Inner Self, component of Spiritual Intelligence and Emotional Intelligence of the students studying at secondary level. Thus null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between The Inner Self, component of Spiritual Intelligence and Emotional Intelligence of the students studying at secondary level is accepted.

The third hypothesis of the study was there is no significant between The Interself, component of Spiritual Intelligence and Emotional Intelligence of the students studying at secondary level. Obtained 'r' value is zero point +0.0797. Thus there is positive but negligible relationship between both the variables. While considering the critical value of 'r' it was found that obtained 'r' value is not significant at both the levels of confidence hence it may be interpreted that no significant relationship exist between The Interself, component of Spiritual Intelligence and Emotional Intelligence of the students studying at secondary level. Thus null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between The Interself, component of Spiritual Intelligence and Emotional Intelligence of the students studying at secondary level is accepted.

The fourth hypothesis of the study was there is no significant between Biostoria, component of Spiritual Intelligence and Emotional Intelligence of the students studying at secondary level. Obtained 'r' value zero point +0.1611. Thus there is positive but negligible relationship between both the variables. While considering the critical value of 'r' it was found that obtained 'r' value is not significant at both the levels of confidence hence it may be interpreted that no significant relationship exist between Biostoria, component of Spiritual Intelligence and Emotional Intelligence of the students studying at secondary level. Thus null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between Biostoria, component of Spiritual Intelligence and Emotional Intelligence of the students studying at secondary level is accepted.

The fifth hypothesis of the study was there is no significant between Life Perspectives, component of Spiritual Intelligence and Emotional Intelligence of the students studying at secondary level. Obtained 'r' value is zero point +0.1611. Thus there is positive but negligible relationship between both the variables. While considering the critical value of 'r' it was found that obtained 'r' value is not significant at both the levels of confidence hence it may be interpreted that no significant relationship exist between Life Perspectives, component of Spiritual Intelligence and Emotional Intelligence of the students studying at secondary level. Thus null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between Life Perspectives, component of Spiritual Intelligence and Emotional Intelligence of the students studying at secondary level is accepted.

The sixth hypothesis of the study was there is no significant between Spiritual Actualization, component of Spiritual Intelligence and Emotional Intelligence of the students studying at secondary level. Obtained 'r' value is zero point +0.1240. Thus there is positive but negligible relationship between both the variables. While considering the critical value of 'r' it was found that obtained 'r' value is not significant at both the levels of confidence hence it may be interpreted that no significant relationship exist between Spiritual Actualization, component of Spiritual Intelligence and Emotional Intelligence of the students studying at secondary level. Thus null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between Spiritual Actualization, component of Spiritual Intelligence and Emotional Intelligence of the students studying at secondary level is accepted.

The seventh hypothesis of the study was there is no significant between Value Orientation, Component of Spiritual Intelligence and Emotional Intelligence of the students studying at secondary level. Obtained 'r' value is zero point +0.2633. Thus there is positive but negligible relationship between both the variables. While considering the critical value of 'r' it was found that obtained 'r' value is significant at 0.01 and 0.05 level of confidence hence it may be interpreted that significant

relationship exist between Value Orientation, component of Spiritual Intelligence and Emotional Intelligence of the students studying at secondary level. Thus null hypothesis that there is significant relationship between Spiritual Intelligence and Emotional Intelligence of the students studying at secondary level is rejected. Sign that Value Orientation, component of Spiritual Intelligence and Emotional Intelligence of the students studying at secondary level have positive correlation.

Conclusion

In this study we find the relationship between Emotional Spiritual and Emotional Intelligence based upon the correlation coefficients presented through the table.

Implication of the Findings

1. The findings of the study have practical implications for secondary school students.
2. The present study is useful for present scenario as well as for future. It is useful for parents, teachers and also for students. With the help of this study we can understand how spiritual intelligence is related to emotional intelligence and how can we improve the emotional intelligence with the help of spiritual intelligence.
3. Present study helps to understand the spiritual intelligence and emotional intelligence and use it to grow up on various ways of success.
4. Once students is aware of how emotions affects his attitude, behavior and society towards situations he will be able to self manage by understanding and being able to control his emotions.
5. Spiritual Intelligence and Emotional Intelligence can be learned and gradually developed. So, the Spiritual, and emotional literacy program should be organized for student teachers.
6. It is hoped that these findings will become worthwhile material for existing domain of education.

References

- Das Alaka (2016) "A Study on Emotional Intelligence in Relation to General Intelligence and Spiritual Intelligence." Indian Journal of Applied Research, Volume : 6 | Issue : 8 | August 2016 | ISSN - 2249555X | IF : 3.919 | IC Value : 74.50, pp 308-310.
- Kotnala Sushma (2015) "A Study of Spiritual Intelligence among Graduate Students." The International Journal of Indian Psychology, ISSN 2348-5396 (e) | ISSN: 2349-3429 (p), Volume 3, Issue 1, No.5, DIP: C00388V3I12015, <http://www.ijip.in> | October - December, 2015, pp.132-140.
- Mangal S.K. and Mangal Shubhra. (2012) Manual for Emotional Intelligence Inventory (EII). National Psychological Corporation, 4/230, Kacheri Ghat, Agra-282004 (India), www.npcindia.com
- Sharma P. & Jain Purnima (2018) "A correlation study of Spiritual Intelligence and Emotional Intelligence of senior secondary school teacher." Aarhat Multidisciplinary International Education Research Journal (AMIERJ), A Peer Reviewed Multidisciplinary Journal, Impact Factor 5.18 UGC Approved Journal No 48178, 48818, ISSN 2278-5655, Vol VI Issues No.I, www.aarhat.com, Dec-Jan 2018 pp.269-274.
- Srivastava Prem S.(2016) "Spiritual intelligence: An overview." International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Development Online ISSN: 2349-4182, Print ISSN: 2349-5979, Impact Factor: RJIF 5.72, www.allsubjectjournal.com , Volume 3; Issue 3; March 2016; Page No. 224-227, <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/321875385>
- Sutar Sulbha S. , Patil Jeevan R. (2018) "A Co-relational Study of Emotional Intelligence and Mental Health among MPSC Students." The International Journal of Indian Psychology, ISSN 2348-5396 (e) | ISSN: 2349-3429 (p) Volume 6, Issue 2, DIP: 18.01.237/20180602 DOI: 10.25215/0602.237, <http://www.ijip.in> | April - June, 2018.
- Zainuddin Roquiya and Ahmed Anjum (2010) Manual for Roqan Spiritual Intelligence Test (RSIT), National Psychological Corporations, 4/230, Kacheri Ghat, Agra-282004 (India).

